

ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES ON THE BASIS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284394>

Abstract. *The most important features of the organization of educational activities in the system of developmental education, the ideas of educational activities and the work of scientists in the Eurasian region are highlighted. It should be especially emphasized that external contradictions (in principle, there are no pure external contradictions: in any case, contradictions concern the individual, his inner world, but one cannot fail to take into account the role of external events that influence the formation of contradictions) in themselves cannot become the engine of development. At the very least, a person should see this contradiction. It is quite possible for a situation when a person does not notice that she has “grown out of the clothes” of her usual existence, that she can handle much more complex tasks.*

Keywords: *developmental education, educational system, educational activities, schoolchild.*

Attempts to define the concept of “education” are being made almost all socio-humanitarian disciplines. For example, philosophers understand education as the process of an individual’s assimilation of sociocultural experience. In this way, they bring education closer to social formation as a whole. Sociologists limit education to processes training and assimilation by an individual of values, norms, attitudes, patterns of behavior inherent in a given society, social group, segment of the population. Psychologists consider education as the most complex type of formation of the individual and the team, based on learning, but supplementing it with connections between the experience acquired in the learning process and properties of the orientation of this particular individual.

One of the most important features of the organization of educational activities in the developmental education system is the use of collective-group work, the organization of communication between educational subjects. This idea is based on the law of development of human higher mental functions described by L.S. Vygotsky. L.S. Vygotsky noted that "at the beginning, there is a debate in the children's community, and with it the need to prove one's point of view, and only after that, reasoning appears in the child as a specific background of internal activity, the characteristic of which is that the child learns to understand and check the foundations of his opinion" [7 p. 1 3].

Adding the basic genetic law to the process of teaching children, L.S. Vygotsky creates zones of close development of learning, calls and activates a number of internal development processes, which at the initial stages are "interactions with others and cooperation with peers can be implemented in the field, but having experienced internal development, they become the internal achievement of the child" [1, p. 388].

In the first stages of formation of educational activity, it is performed with the subject of the team. At the beginning, elementary school students perform educational activities together, using each other in accepting and solving educational tasks, conducting dialogues and choosing the best actions and best solutions. organizes extended debates. It is in these situations that the

zones of their proximal development occur in children. But little by little, each child becomes its individual subject and begins to carry out this activity independently [2, p. 67].

Thus, in the process of applying developmental education, the educational dialogue, which is considered as a collaborative product of research activities, is the basis for organizing educational activities [3]. Organization of educational discussion "helps to increase the independence of elementary school students, to strive to act on their own initiative, to restore interest in learning, to develop critical thinking" [4, p. 37]. Educational discussion, creation of situations that create dialogue between the subjects of cognitive activity is considered an effective means of developmental education.

Literature analysis and methods. Educational activity, thus, is considered the leading activity of a primary school student, not only develops theoretical thinking and voluntary behavior, but also has a significant impact on children's personality, needs and motivations.

Educational activity and subject theory G.N. Vergeles [5, 6], V.V. Davidov [7], A.N. Leontev [8], A.K. It is given in the works of Markova [9, 10] and others. In this theory, it is not about the acquisition of knowledge skills by a person in general, but about the acquisition that is carried out in the form of a specific educational activity. The assimilation of this or that knowledge in the form of educational activity with a school student begins with the creative transformation of the material to be mastered.

Educational activities are the main components, as it is known, educational needs, motives, tasks, actions and processes. Children entering the first grade certainly do not have a whole structure of it. It is formed in some children for several years, and accelerates especially in primary grades. As it was noted, educational activity at the junior school age is considered the main and important among other types of children's activities. Performance by elementary school students "determines the formation of new primary mental formations and, above all, the basis of theoretical thinking aimed at clarifying the development of legal subjects"

In a broad social sense, education is the transfer of accumulated experience from older generations to younger ones. Experience is understood as knowledge, skills, ways of thinking, moral, ethical, legal norms known to people, in a word, the entire spiritual heritage of humanity created in the process of historical development." In a narrow social sense, education is understood as "directed influence on a person by social institutions with the aim of forming in him certain knowledge, views, beliefs, moral values, political orientation, preparation for life." "In a broad pedagogical sense, education is a specially organized, purposeful and controlled influence of the team, educators on the student in order to develop specified qualities in him, carried out in educational institutions and covering the entire educational process." "In the narrow pedagogical sense, education is this is the process and result of educational work aimed at solving specific educational problems."

Showing the role of theoretical knowledge and meaningful generalizations in the construction of developmental education, L.V. Zankov, V.V. Unlike Davidov, he does not limit the developmental functions of education by focusing on theoretical thinking, but connects them with the child's mind, will, and emotions, in which case, "it is a deep mistake to divide thinking into empirical and theoretical as independent forms of perception." However, for the purposes of researching a specific problem and solving specific problems, such a distribution is possible.

In the science of psychology, the concept of "educational activity" is considered in various aspects [5, 6, 7, 8, 10]. For example, N.F. Talizina considers educational activities as one of the

leading types of activities that ensure the formation and development of a child's personality in the process of acquiring knowledge consisting of specific and general actions [11]. Specific learning activities ensure the acquisition of knowledge in its specific content;

Results: As a result of the organization of educational activities in the developmental education system, a) observation; b) abstract thinking - analysis, synthesis, abstraction, generalization; c) practical actions - helps in forming the ability to create a material object.

Students must master the operations of thought through which knowledge is assimilated and controlled. Developmental education is teaching, its content, methods and forms are based on the laws of child development.

The implementation of educational activities requires special attention from the teacher to the complete and correct implementation of the actions and processes with the help of which educational tasks should be solved by schoolchildren: changing the condition of the problem ; modeling of the relationship separated in the educational task to be solved in the form of an object, graphic or symbol; change it again in order to study in detail the characteristics of the relationship isolated in the model.

In recent years, the question has been actively debated: is it Is education a process of influence or interaction? Sometimes discussions in this area are reminiscent of medieval debates held on the problem: which came first - the chicken or the egg? It is very problematic to separate impact from interaction in the educational process. Any process is a sequential change of states in the development of something. This is especially true for the pedagogical process, the speed and unpredictability of which amaze the imagination.

It is quite possible to consider the educational process at one stage of its development as an impact, at another – as an interaction. But in principle there is reason to talk about the inextricable nature of the relationships connecting influence and interaction in the educational process, if only because any influence of one subject on another entails followed by a reaction (passive or active) from the latter. The acquisition of theoretical knowledge and appropriate skills and abilities by schoolchildren takes place in solving educational tasks. Solving such tasks allows students to learn something general before mastering their specific aspects. Thus, the main method of developmental education is the method of introducing children to the situation of educational tasks and organizing educational activities to solve them.

Thus, education is both a process and a result, and interaction and impact. As a process, it serves as a means of transmitting social experience; as a result, it contributes to the development, formation and formation of a person, and, consequently, his socialization, personalization and individualization; as interaction it means a continuous interdependent process of actions participants in the educational process; as an influence, it allows for greater activity of one of the latter at one or another stage of the educational process. Educational activity is considered to be the leading activity of a primary school teacher, and it not only develops theoretical thinking and discretionary behavior, but also has a significant impact on children's personality, needs and motivations.

All-round has modern knowledge, has high spiritual and ethical qualities, independent, critical and creative thinking and highly qualified pedagogical staff, teachers are engaged in the future, students are interested in the youth, they create new things, and they work tirelessly on their own.

REFERENCES

1. Vygotsky L.S. The problem of learning and mental development at school age. // Pedagogical psychology. M.: Pedagogy, 1991. - S. 374-390.
1. Zukerman Types of Communication in Education. - Tomsk, PELENG, 1993.
2. Lebedeva V.P., Orlov V.A., Panov V.I. Psychodidactic aspects of developmental learning // Pedagogy. - No. 6. - S. 25-30.
3. Antropova M.V., Borodkina G.V. Kuznetsova L.M., Manke G.G. Physiological-hygienic assessment of developmental learning in primary classes // Pedagogy. 1999. - No. 8. - S. 35-41.
4. Vergeles G.I. Formation of educational activity as a problem of didactics // Junior schoolchild as a subject of pedagogical influence: Interuniversity. Sat. scientific works / Ed. G.I. Vergeles. - L. Publishing house LGPI, 1989.-P. 54-73.
5. Vergeles G.I. Formation of educational activities of junior schoolchildren on the basis of interdisciplinary connections: Textbook. allowance. - L., Publishing House LGPI, 1987. - 80 p.
6. Davydov V.V. Psychological theory of educational activity and a method of initial teaching based on meaningful generalization. - Tomsk: Peleng, 1992. - 114 p.
7. Leontyev A.N. Problems of activity in psychology // Questions of philosophy. - 1972. - No. 9. - P. 95-109
8. Markova A.K. Forming interest in learning among schoolchildren. - M.: Pedagogy, 1986. - 113 p.
9. Markova A.K. Formation of learning motivation at school age. M.: Education, 1983. - 96 p.
10. Talizina N.F. Pedagogical psychology: Textbook. Benefit. M.: Publishing center "Academy", 1998. - 288 p.
11. Sultanova U.M. Rivojlantiruvchi ta'lim metodologiyasi va texnologiyasi xalqaro ilmiy jurnali No. 4(95) 2022 y.
12. M.M.Sultanov, U.M.Sultanova L.M.Saydaliyeva Pedagogical- psychological aspects of students' logical thinking development. European Chemical Bulletin Section A-Research paper ISSN 2063-5346. 2023.- 16108-16117
13. Sultanova U.M. Method of introducing the concept of symmetry to elementary school students. theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences International scientific-online conference.